

A COMPREHENSIVE MECHANISM TO OPTIMIZE THE LEVEL OF EFFICIENCY OF SECURITY IN PUBLIC PLACES IN THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT AS A PRECONDITION FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND SMART CITIES

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Abstract

The objective of this conceptual paper is to map in a comprehensive and systematic way the set of mechanisms and activities used by public authorities and institutions to ensure the protection of order and security in public places in the urban environment. This is the case of Russia, for example. The protection of public order and ensuring public safety is a priority task of the activities of state internal affairs bodies and a necessary condition for any tourist activity, and particularly a problem for large cities since the existence of various governmental structures and public institutions are involved can hinder the process. By means of a documentary study, taking as an example the case of Russia, several factors affecting the safety of the urban environment have been considered, such as: public space, law, and order, public safety, the formation of a safe material urban environment. Also, various areas of activity in the functioning of the complex mechanism, the participating authorities and public institutions, their functions, and their role have been investigated, taking the Russian case as an example. The authors identified examples of successful solutions to problems of ensuring security and law and order in public places from Russian experience and supplemented by the international one. It has been concluded that proper provision of security and law and order in public places is achievable only in a complex, by combining the efforts of various state structures and the public. The ways to improve their activities have been proposed.

Keywords: Public safety; Law and order; Public place; Activities of authorized bodies; Public participation; Tourism.

UM MECANISMO ABRANGENTE PARA OTIMIZAR O NÍVEL DE EFICIÊNCIA DA SEGURANÇA EM LOCAIS PÚBLICOS DO AMBIENTE URBANO COMO PRÉ-CONDIÇÃO PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO TURÍSTICO E DE CIDADES INTELIGENTES

Resumo

O objetivo desta artigo conceitual é mapear de forma integral e sistemática o conjunto de mecanismos e de atividades usados pelas autoridades e instituições públicas para assegurar a proteção da ordem e da segurança em locais públicos no ambiente urbano. , tomando como exemplo o caso da Rússia. A proteção da ordem pública e a garantia da segurança pública são uma tarefa prioritária das atividades dos organismos de assuntos internos ao Estado e condição necessária para qualquer atividade turística e, particularmente um problema para as grandes cidades dado que a existência de várias estruturas governamentais e instituições públicas estão envolvidas podem dificultar o processo. Por meio de um estudo documental, tomando como exemplo o caso da Rússia, foram considerados vários fatores que afetam a segurança do ambiente urbano, tais como: espaço público, lei e ordem pública, segurança pública, formação de um ambiente urbano material seguro. Foram investigadas várias áreas de atividade no funcionamento do complexo mecanismo, as autoridades e instituições públicas participantes, as suas funções, e o seu papel. Os autores identificaram exemplos de soluções bem-sucedidas para problemas de garantia de segurança e ordem pública em locais públicos, a partir da experiência russa e suplementada pela internacional. Concluiu-se que a provisão adequada de segurança e ordem pública em locais públicos só é possível num complexo, combinando os esforços de várias estruturas estatais e do público. As formas de melhorar as suas atividades foram propostas.

Palavras-chave: Segurança pública; Lei e ordem pública; Lugar público; Atividades de organismos autorizados; Participação; Tourism.

UN MECANISMO INTEGRAL PARA OPTIMIZAR EL NIVEL DE EFICACIA DE LA SEGURIDAD EN LOS LUGARES PÚBLICOS DEL ENTORNO URBANO COMO CONDICIÓN PREVIA PARA EL DESARROLLO DEL TURISMO Y LAS CIUDADES INTELIGENTES

Resumen

El objetivo de este documento conceptual es cartografiar de forma exhaustiva y sistemática el conjunto de mecanismos y actividades utilizados por las autoridades e instituciones públicas para garantizar la protección del orden y la seguridad en los lugares públicos del entorno urbano. El marco conceptual se basa en el caso de Rusia. La protección del orden público y la garantía de la seguridad ciudadana es una tarea prioritaria de las actividades de los órganos estatales de interior y una condición necesaria para cualquier actividad turística, y particularmente un problema para las grandes ciudades, ya que la existencia de diversas estructuras gubernamentales e instituciones públicas implicadas puede dificultar el proceso. A través de un estudio documental, tomando como ejemplo el caso de Rusia, se han considerado diversos factores que afectan a la seguridad del entorno urbano, tales como: espacio público, ley y orden, seguridad pública, la formación de un entorno urbano material seguro. Se han investigado diversas áreas de actividad en el funcionamiento del complejo mecanismo, las autoridades e instituciones públicas participantes, sus funciones y su papel. En el curso del estudio, los autores identificaron ejemplos de soluciones exitosas a los problemas de garantizar la seguridad y el orden público en lugares públicos a partir de la experiencia rusa e internacional. Se ha llegado a la conclusión de que la provisión adecuada de seguridad y orden público en lugares públicos sólo se puede lograr en un complejo, combinando los esfuerzos de varias estructuras estatales y del público. Se han propuesto las formas de mejorar sus actividades.

Palabras clave: Seguridad pública; Lugar público; Ley y orden; Actividades de los organismos autorizados; Participación; Tourism.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In any state, regardless of the political regime, social, and state structure, there are needs that do not lose their significance and would be relevant in different epochs of human existence (considering the development of society at that time). Law and order and security are among the needs of people who have now been enshrined in the vast majority of constitutions or normative documents.

The function of ensuring law and order and public security is a traditional function of the state, inherent in it since its inception (Pimentel, 2020). This is the most important function of the state and is carried out, as a rule, by specially created public authorities (Demichev et al., 2021).

It is important to note here that the functioning of a rule-of-law state with a democratic regime presupposes the existence of a developed civil society. The development of civic initiatives related to the protection of public order and public safety is in line with the development of civil societies (Lochmann et al., 2022). Therefore, it is necessary to ensure coordination of citizens and internal affairs bodies in ensuring public order and public safety, which will greatly strengthen the preventive effect on offenders, will contribute to the suppression of offenses and the punishment of perpetrators (Svirin et al., 2021).

Considering this context, our research hypothesis is that the greatest effectiveness of ensuring the safety of public places of the urban environment is achieved through the multidimensional interrelated activities of competent and interested authorities, non-governmental organizations, and public institutions.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Security, Public Urban Spaces and Authority Bodies

Security and law and order play an important role in the development of modern cities. The urban environment today is the main human habitat. As of 2020, 56.2% of the world's population lived in cities (The World Bank, 2018). Therefore, along with the general problems of personal security and law enforcement, the environment of a modern city forms several other security problems related to urban areas and is unusual for other types of territories. Therewith, their relevance will only increase considering the existing trends of urban population growth (68.6% of the World's population is expected in 2050) (Worldometer, n.d.).

Living together in an urban environment, a sufficiently large population density of cities is the

reason that today a citizen outside of his/her personal space, home, contacts other people unfamiliar to him/her, entering into public relations in places that are commonly called public places.

The accessibility of such places to various people, including potential offenders, the possibility of conflict, and criminal situations lead to the fact that a person is most vulnerable in public places, including from crime, while security requirements are often met only formally. According to Gavrilov et al. (2022), a person needs more protection in public places, and the numerous problems of ensuring public law and order and public safety, the current high level of offenses, weak control of public authorities over certain spheres of life may cause the need to improve some elements of the law enforcement system of the Russian Federation.

The above-mentioned factors arouse a certain interest of researchers in the safety of public places. In Russian context, the various aspects have been analyzed in the scientific research of Otegenov (2021) (organizational and legal foundations for ensuring public security), Kononov (2020) (participation of non-state institutions in the implementation of the public function of ensuring public security), Polyantseva (2021) (planning and control of the territory, considering the requirements of public safety), and many others.

The authors of the studies available for study consider various aspects of the mentioned issues within the framework of narrow specialization, without trying to imagine the activities of various government structures, private organizations, and public institutions to ensure the safety of public places in the complex. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of the protection of public places seems very relevant.

The studied literature shows that the factors influencing the safety of the environment are: population density, the social and ethnic composition of the population, building features, and technical equipment with security systems. Let us consider each factor separately (Luna, 2020).

Population density is a natural factor that has the most significant impact on the safety of the public environment. This factor is predetermined: in many cases, it is historically established and, in a democratic state, is practically not amenable to regulatory influence. Accounting for this factor in the formation of a safe environment requires an integrated approach, focusing regulatory and managerial efforts in all areas: regulatory, legal, organizational, and administrative (law enforcement, involving commercial security structures and the population, creating socio-economic conditions for the population, etc.).

The socio-ethnic composition is a factor that also requires an integrated approach; in its regulation, the actions of both local authorities and the central

leadership are of great importance. This factor can be controlled by creating an environment that minimizes and excludes the possibility of ethnic conflicts through the implementation of a well-thought-out, diverse, and consistent social, national-ethnic, and immigration policy (Lapointe et al., 2021).

A significant role in the safety of public places is played by the features of the development of the settlement and the layout of public places: streets, parks, squares, and residential and industrial zones. Naturally, places where infill development already exists are already quite difficult to change. However, if there is the will on the part of the local authorities and material possibilities, these difficulties are gradually resolved.

It is important to competently approach the planning and design of new urban areas. When designing public places in settlements, the interests of public safety are not always considered. Incorrect planning and poor location, which make it difficult to provide the necessary lighting and real-time video surveillance of the situation in public places, provoke potential offenders to commit acts that threaten public safety.

The technical equipment of security systems today is an essential factor and, at the same time, the easiest way to ensure the safety of public places, considering the rapidly developing and more and more accessible technologies, including in the field of security. Strengthening this factor can be implemented through the integration of security tasks into the smart city life support system, which is being introduced in several places so far as an experiment. Naturally, this will require the availability of the necessary material resources and qualified specialists in the development, installation, and maintenance of the system.

2.2 Tourism and Security in the Urban Public Space

By its turn, in the international literature... (Allis & dos Santos Moraes, 2022; Fernandes, 2013, Hall, 2005; Harvey, 1999; among others) considering the perspective of time-space compression, which claims that nowadays, the possibility of locomotion and transportation of people, especially motivated by the tourist experience, make places increasingly close and accessible to all, qualified by the extensive literature as tourists. In this sense, the practice of tourism turns public places into propitious spaces for public questions about security, resilience, diversity, and sustainability.

From studies on the history of tourism (Badaró, 2003; Feruza, 2022; Zuelow, 2015), it is possible to deduce that people have always traveled, as a means of protection, trade, conquest, curiosity or leisure, usually eager for the possibility of experiencing new experiences in a different reality to which they are

accustomed. Therefore, since the times of the migratory flows of primitive peoples, people have been traveling under increasingly wider conditions (Goeldner & Brent Ritchie, 2002), heading to more and more distant places, which lack public safety policies, considering the diversity of people that tourist destinations attract (Stankova, 2022).

In this sense, tourist places induce people to move in search of new experiences, consumption of products and services, especially the creation of images and feelings. Among these inducers, culture, creativity, hospitality and technologies, historical and heritage context, predominantly identified in public places, stand out (Richards & Duif, 2018).

Regarding the institutional perspectives coming from the State, the political-administrative instances of governance stand out, responsible for representing and defining the form of management and development of the places that induce tourism. Also incorporated in this dimension is the host community, which besides acting in the reception, service, and assistance to tourists, constitutes a network of actors to designate a potentially tourist destination. Through coparticipative actions, these instances of governance, together with other state and non-state agencies, usually adopt strategies to ensure order and safety of tourists and local citizens, making public places more resilient and inclusive (Mediotte et al, 2020).

It is observed in the tourism literature that tourism-inducing public places are dynamic, being subject to transformations due to internal and, mainly, external forces, which cause impacts on the geographic-economic dynamics of tourism territories, as in cases of crises (Emmendoerfer & Mediotte, 2022) caused by pandemics, epidemics, natural disasters, violence and wars, and other adversities, which compromise the access routes and circulation of tourists.

Therefore, such impacts can influence the emotions of mobilities in times of instability, which tend to reproduce new socio-economic relations, new forms of consumption, new connections with tourist public places, their spaces and environments, political-ideological and governance beliefs, new aesthetic and leisure perspectives (Mediotte et al, 2020). Therefore, tourism is constituted in a management optics [Table 1], focused on the movement and development of tourist demands, revealing a global-local scenario, as well as the motives and the diversified elements that induce the tourist to his final destination, even if it is temporary.

In this sense, it is worth pointing out that the compression of time and space that tourism produces influences not only the dynamization of transport and communication flows, but also the very construction of a new identity, especially in the perspective of territorial reengineering and ludification or territorial

(re)signification, based on the guarantee of security, resilience, inclusion, and local sustainability.

Table 1. Summary of the Conceptual Perspective Tourism, Public Places, and Security.

Hall, Williams & Lew (2014); Pender & Sharpley (2005); Smith (1994)	Tourism	A process socially constructed and, in its complexity, constituted by dynamic systems: i) in the first place, the tourist, who has an active role in the production and maintenance of tourist public places; ii) the products and services from the tourist trade that, besides the provision of services, recognizes the generation of potentialities and multicultural processes of a globalized context; iii) creativity as an element of integration instead of fragmentation and segmentation; iv) experiences as an object of value creation, images and multisensorial aspects, different from the usual ones.
Le-Klaehn & Hall (2015); Konzen (2013); Strain (1996)	Public Places	They are often understood as fixed spaces where events are recorded and planned, where flows originate, based on the concept of location, properties, the design of border demarcations, urbanization, where the entities representing the state are delimited
Hall, Timothy, Duval (2012); Henok (2021), Stankova (2022)	Security	It influences and ensures not only the protection of the dynamization of transport flows, communication, people and products, but also in the very perception and construction of local identity and symbology, especially in the perspective of reengineering, ludification or territorial (re)signification between tourists and citizens.

Source: own elaboration.

3 METHOD

The presented research was carried out based on the principles of systemic, functional, and integrated approaches, which made it possible to present the activities to ensure the safety of public places of the urban environment as complex and systemic.

The set goal and the need to solve related research tasks required the use of a large number of general scientific and special methods of a qualitative and quantitative nature. The statistical method allowed presenting the ubiquity and depth of the existing problems. The method of system analysis helped to track and link different types of activities, but common in orientation, in a single mechanism.

The method of transition from a general concept to a particular one was used to determine the role of various bodies, structures, and institutions in the functioning of this mechanism. The comparative legal method allowed turning to world practice to search for successful schemes for ensuring the security of urban areas.

The hypothesis of the study was proved based on data obtained from such information materials as regulatory legal acts, published scientific papers with research on various aspects of public safety, official statistics, and other related information from trusted sources on the Internet. Special research methods were also used in proving the hypothesis: analysis of documents and an expert survey to assess the impact of the design, creation, and condition of urban areas on the safety of public places.

Thirty-two employees of the internal affairs bodies were interviewed.

The criteria for selecting experts were whether they had articles on this topic published in journals included in the Scopus or Web of Science citation databases in the amount of at least 3 or at least 10

years of work experience in ensuring urban safety.

For them, an expert survey was conducted to assess the impact of various factors on the safety of public places.

Experts were sent e-mails asking them to assess the impact of various factors characterizing the urban environment on the safety of public places. The authors were told on what topic the research is being conducted on and what hypothesis is being put forward in the work.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Context and Object of Study Characterization

First of all, it seems necessary for this study to consider the concept of a public place, especially considering the fact that it is not clearly fixed in regulatory legal acts.

Thus, Part 1 of Article 20.20 of the Code of Administrative Offences of the Russian Federation (State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation, 2001) provides a list of public places: children's, educational and medical organizations, all types of public transport of urban and suburban communication, cultural organizations (except for organizations or catering facilities located in them, including those without the formation of a legal entity), health and fitness and sports facilities. In Part 2 of

Article 20.20 of the Code of Administrative Offences of the Russian Federation – these are streets, stadiums, public gardens, parks, public transport vehicles, and other public places. It follows from the types of public places listed above that the definition of a public place cannot be narrowed down to places of free access: not all public places can be free for access to an indefinite circle of people since there are places where people's access is restricted or allowed only under certain conditions.

Such places, for example, can be the departure hall of passengers at the airport, where access is allowed only upon presentation of a plane ticket; a stadium, a cinema, where it is possible to go with a ticket, and other similar places.

Considering this circumstance, the legal definition of public places should not be tied to the list of public places. It is advisable to rely on the sign of free or possible access for an unlimited number of people when formulating it.

Ensuring the safety of citizens in public places, creating safe conditions for their life is the purpose and main responsibility of the police of the Russian Federation. This duty is not only enshrined in Article 1 of the Federal Law "On Police" (State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation, 2011) but is also regularly updated by the leadership of the Russian Federation.

In particular, speaking at an expanded meeting of the board of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia, V. Putin pointed out that "... it is your (the internal affairs) direct responsibility to make people in their yard, entrance, village, city feel safe and protected" (Session of the Collegium, 2020).

The essence of the safety of citizens in public places is closely related to the concept of public order since it's strengthening undoubtedly contributes to improving public safety.

Public order is the normal functioning of public relations, the absence of risks and threats that can disrupt the normal life of people and their progressive social and professional development, the creation of an atmosphere of calm and protection of the personality and property of people, individuals and legal entities (Otegenov, 2021).

Public order creates all the conditions necessary to ensure public safety, making the relevant legal categories dependent. In the development of Article 132 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, Federal Law No. 131-FZ of October 6, 2003 "On the General Principles of the Organization of local self-government in the Russian Federation" (State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation, 2003) provided for two issues of local importance concerning public order:

- 1) paragraph 8 of Part 1 of Article 15 and paragraph 9 of Part 1 of Article 16 – organization of public order protection on the territory of the municipal district and urban district by municipal police;

- 2) paragraph 33 of part 1 of Article 14 and paragraph 37 of Part 1 of Article 16 – the creation of conditions for the activities of voluntary formations of the population to protect public order (in settlements and urban districts).

Consequently, the legislator has fixed two ways for municipalities to protect public order on their territory: by professional bodies and public forces. However, if the Law "On Militia" (Supreme Soviet of the Russian Federation, 1991) provided for the existence of municipal public order protection bodies (Part 2 of Article 3), then the Law "On Police" that replaced it, which reformed the system of internal affairs bodies, does not provide for the creation of municipal police bodies in one form or another

However, it proceeds from the fact that the police is an integral part of a unified centralized system of the federal executive authority in the field of internal affairs, the legal and financial basis of which is exclusively federal sources. Thus, with common security tasks for different branches of government, some inconsistency in their actions is possible.

The international experience of interaction between the authorities in maintaining public security is of interest to the Russian Federation, which continues to search for effective forms of cooperation between federal, regional, and municipal government, its place in the implementation of national functions. The experience of the United Kingdom is of particular interest in this regard since municipal and regional (self)management has historically received significant development in this country (Pronkin, 2021).

Responsibility for maintaining law and order in Greater London is assigned, on the one hand, to its Administration, on the other, to its police (Metropolitan Police), which is controlled by the city administration politically, but administratively acts independently, reporting to the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Administratively, the local police are not subordinate to the district authorities. The latter can finance the police programs in which they are interested. Their influence on the work of the police is also carried out through various partnerships. New partnerships were formed in London in 2014 – to reduce crime and disorder (Crime and Disorder Reduction Partnerships, CDRPs) (Travers, 2015).

Their main task was to ensure the cooperation of local authorities and services in the fight against crime and antisocial behavior. Therefore, as the Crime and Disorder Act adopted in 1998 required, (The Parliament of the United Kingdom, 1998) in partnership, along with representatives of the police, city and local administrations, probation services, fire, medical, educational, and others were represented.

Residents can maintain contacts with the police through special councils for local security (Safer Neighborhood Boards, SNB), which were created in each borough (administrative units of London). They include police chiefs, municipal councilors, local

businessmen, and representatives of social groups. Their meetings are public.

The Boards unite the police and communities in determining priorities in the fight against crime, joint participation in this fight, and ensuring cooperation in a wide range of issues related to public safety. Representatives of civil society can participate directly in law enforcement and control over the police. The voluntary Neighborhood watch helps to solve the first task, the second one is provided by Stop and search monitoring groups (Pronkin, 2021).

London municipal districts consider the fight against minor offenses and "antisocial behavior" to be their priority task. The latter is considered as actions that violate the legitimate rights of other people or cause them concern. In these cases, municipal authorities act as coordinators of the actions of various structures and persons interested in suppressing antisocial behavior (Pronkin, 2021).

The security of public places in the USA is handled by the district and local police, which are directly subordinate to local governments. The police department reports directly to the city council or the mayor. In other words, the local police in the USA is an independent unit with its budget, directly subordinated to the local civil self-government of the lowest of the existing levels.

The city police is organized hierarchically in large cities governed by a single municipality, but the essence remains the same – for example, New York is divided into 115 precincts, the management of which is closed to the city police department, subordinate to the mayor's office (Paneyakh, 2011). Active assistance to the police is provided by the population within the framework of the "Neighborhood Watch" program introduced in the USA in 1972. The role of "Neighborhood Watch" groups is only to conduct surveillance in ensuring the safety of public places.

Numerous examples, both from Russian and world practice, show that the implementation of the law enforcement function today is not always a monopoly of state or local self-government bodies.

The legal basis for cooperation between the police and the population has been formed in the Russian Federation. The procedure for the creation and operation of voluntary people's squads, guarantees of the legal protection of people's vigilantes and freelance police officers, conditions for their material incentives, the provision of benefits and compensation have been determined (State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation, 2014).

Citizens' participation in ensuring the safety of public places in the Russian Federation is provided for in the form of citizens' participation in the activities of law enforcement-oriented public associations. The

Russian practice of organizing voluntary participation of citizens in the protection of public order, based on the rich Soviet experience, knows a variety of types of implementations of these forms.

These are environmental, road patrols, Cossack squads, and student (youth) law enforcement detachments. As of January 1, 2020, the public formations that assist the internal affairs bodies in maintaining public order and preventing offenses include 12.7 thousand public organizations with a total number of 348.9 thousand people, of which 10.5 thousand are people's guards (184 thousand people) and 1.4 thousand are Cossack (146.8 thousand people) squads, as well as 18.1 thousand freelance police officers (Ministry of Interior of Russia, 2020).

Often there is a transfer of certain components of this public function and, consequently, the corresponding powers from the sphere of state and municipal administration to private law and public institutions, which indicates certain trends in the use of mechanisms of privatization ("de-socialization") of the functions of public power and participation in modern public administration (Kononov, 2020).

The issue of the possibilities of using and developing non-state forms of law enforcement and public security in the country as one of the promising areas of implementation of the National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation (President of the Russian Federation, 2015) and the Concept of Public Security in the Russian Federation (President of the Russian Federation, 2013) is on the agenda. Thus, in recent years, the state has found it expedient to transfer functions in the field of flight safety, rail transportation, postal communications to private law entities.

The use of private-law forms of implementation of the public function of law enforcement and public security today is carried out through the provision of public services under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia, Federal National Guard Troops Service through their subordinate institutions or other organizations, outsourcing, i.e. the transfer on a competitive basis of some police functions to the private sector, the conclusion of concession agreements and administrative agreements with subjects of private law.

Assistance in the protection of public safety to law enforcement agencies by organizations engaged in private security activities can also be considered a form of public-private partnership. Therewith, the range of responsibilities for ensuring law and order and public safety that can be assigned to the PSC, as in the case of voluntary associations of citizens for the protection of law and order, excludes any independence in the implementation of this function and is limited only to participation in activities carried out by internal affairs

bodies and assistance to them, assistance to citizens in calling on-duty services, informing law enforcement agencies about violations of public order that have become known to them, preparing, committing and committed offenses.

In world practice, for example, in several US states, Canada, South Africa, and the UK, along with various police formations that are state or municipal authorities, private police services provide their services to the population, which accompany cargo, guard banks, monitor security at airports, install alarms and equipment for monitoring protected areas, work as

bodyguards and detectives, independently protect law enforcement, and patrol city neighborhoods.

Therewith, private police officers have the right to carry out civil arrests and collect evidence for the prosecution of private individuals (Pravy argument & Libertarianstvo, 2019).

4.2 Data presentation

The results of the conducted studies of models of interaction of security actors in public places in different countries can be presented in the form of Table 1.

Table 1. Models of interaction of security actors in public places.

Country	The main direct subject of ensuring the safety of public places	Management, coordination, and control bodies, a brief assessment of the relationship with the police	Professional non-state actors in ensuring the safety of public places	Public associations
Great Britain	Police (Interior Ministry)	Local self-government (coordination and control only)		Neighborhood supervision
USA	Local police	Local self-government (Direct subordination)	Private police with extensive capabilities (up to arrests)	Neighborhood supervision
Russia	Police (Interior Ministry)	Local self-government (limited coordination and control capabilities)	Private security organizations with limited legal capabilities	Voluntary people's squads, freelance employees, Cossack detachments

Source: own elaboration.

It should be noted that a huge role in the safety of public places is played by the peculiarities of the development of the settlement, the layout of public places: streets, parks, squares, residential and industrial zones. The survey of internal affairs officers

showed that 63% of respondents believe that the nature of the development significantly affects public safety. Based on the results of the experts' answers, Table 2 was compiled.

Table 2. The impact of the urban environment on the safety of public places

Relative number of expert opinions, %	Population density	Social and ethnic composition of the population	Building Features	Technical equipment with security systems	Assessment of the degree of influence
56	60	63	67	Strong	
26	23	20	17	Weak	
28	17	17	16	Does not affect	

Source: own elaboration.

Naturally, it is already quite difficult to change places where there is already an infill construction. Thus, it is important to correctly approach the planning and design of new urban areas. The interests of public safety are not always taken into account when designing public places in settlements (Rachkova, 2012). Incorrect layout and poor location, the inability to provide the necessary illumination and real-time video surveillance of the situation in public places provoke potential offenders to commit actions that threaten public safety.

5 DISCUSSION

Currently, serious discussions are being raised about the participation of local self-government bodies in ensuring security and law and order in the territory entrusted to them. Several authors (Bezrukov, 2015) note that today, in the conditions of modern Russia, there is an actual detachment of municipal bodies from participating in law enforcement and this leads to the fact that the federal center bears full responsibility for ensuring law and order at all levels of the territorial

organization of the state – from federal cities to small rural settlements and inter-settlement territories. In turn, in a study devoted to the analysis of public order in Poland (Kostrubiec, 2021), the author concludes that the law-making decentralization of the state is necessary for the effective implementation of tasks in the field of public security by local governments.

In Russia, researchers note a tendency to exclude the protection of public order and public safety from the number of issues of local importance in legal regulation (Gadzhiev, 2020). Thus, as a result of the popular vote on amendments to the Constitution of the Russian Federation, revisions were made to Article 132 concerning the exclusion from the powers of local self-government bodies of such a function as "the protection of public order".

The motivation for excluding the provision under consideration from the Constitution of the Russian Federation is not entirely clear, since the relevance of preserving the legal content of the function of ensuring public order at the level of local self-government is obvious since it is this level that is closest to the population (Ignatyuk & Kolesko, 2020; Dukhovnaya et al., 2021).

Perhaps the reason is to improve (control). However, there is a boundary between supervision (control) and accountability in the work of the police, especially law enforcement agencies. For example, police reforms in Indonesia have been linked to the demands of a broader public influence on accountability in the performance of police functions, in particular concerning law enforcement in discretionary cases.

The authors of the study (Indarti, 2020) come to a rather interesting, but ambiguous conclusion that police accountability is required both inside and outside the country, both individually and organizationally to ensure compliance with the laws by the national police, especially concerning discretionary cases.

The implementation of the above function of local self-government is seen by many researchers, including us, in its assignment to the newly created bodies of the municipal police (Otegenov, 2021). The obvious advantages of this are the absence of higher authorities requiring indicators, reporting; subordination of the municipal police to the law, and accountability to the population, which will evaluate the effectiveness of its work. Today, it seems impossible to use the world experience of building effective mechanisms for ensuring public safety and law and order without the municipal police.

Furthermore, it should be noted that the safety of urban public places today is one of the main elements taken into account when creating a comprehensive Smart City program covering all aspects of urban life

(Bondarenko et al., 2020). In this regard, an expert survey was conducted to assess the impact of the design, creation, and condition of urban areas on the safety of public places. Cities are an integral part of the ideology of sustainable development of states (Asaul & Shuan, 2021; Shaimerdenova et al., 2020).

The placement of smart city systems should be carried out in places with the highest population density. There, the system will pass the most stringent reliability tests and show its effectiveness. Such places are subject to increased monitoring by the system, using programs to analyze the behavior of residents, the behavior of existing criminals within the framework of a citizen profiling system combined with a system of probable incident sites, etc.

Today, the design of smart city systems must consider the objectives of stimulating the local economy, optimizing city services, creating a seamless dialogue with citizens, and collecting enough data to understand the habits and needs of citizens. In this regard, an increasingly important task is the provision of the most vulnerable segments of society with the opportunity to take advantage of digital solutions and avoid the negative consequences of digital exclusion.

The concept of a smart city today uses the tactics of thoughtful, reasonable territorial growth, optimization of building density, and search for modern types of buildings and structures, considering the criteria for the safety of public places. Such decisions are made both by changing existing buildings and developing new territories.

In a smart city, the introduction, placement, and use of technical security equipment are of great importance: from simple video surveillance cameras to face recognition systems, with subsequent processing of the received and accumulated data and informing the authorities providing public security.

Although many researchers consider initiatives to create "smart cities" as another step towards excessively strict surveillance of the population (Armo-Sistemy, 2020; Kement et al., 2021), few dispute the usefulness of modern technologies used to organize a safe urban environment: traffic regulation on the roads, crime reduction, and even the spread of viruses.

Thus, safe conditions should be taken into account when planning, designing, and properly equipping public places, which will create a safe environment in settlements.

The analysis made it possible to come to the conclusion about the complex nature of activities to ensure the safety of public places in the urban environment.

The main place in the complex mechanism is occupied by internal affairs bodies that perform their functions of law enforcement and public security in the

form of direct participation in relevant law enforcement activities. The actions of private security structures and voluntary public associations are also of a direct nature, but they play a supporting role.

The organization of general interaction and control within the framework of the mentioned mechanism are entrusted to local self-government bodies. Their competence also includes activities for planning, designing, creating public places in settlements, considering safety requirements. The creation of coordinating Security Councils of the municipality, with the participation of representatives of local authorities, internal affairs bodies, private security businesses, and voluntary public organizations, is seen as an area for improving the organization of ensuring the safety of public places, for better interaction (Gurinovich & Petrykina, 2021).

An even more promising solution seems to be the establishment of municipal police directly subordinate to local authorities, but this will require serious changes in policy and legislation. For the departments responsible for planning, designing, construction, and operation of urban infrastructure, it is necessary to introduce the obligation to develop requirements for the safety of public places and expertise for their implementation. Integration of all the above-mentioned activities into the "Smart City" system also seems promising (Balova et al., 2021).

When designing smart cities, it is necessary to consider all four (main) factors discussed above, which to the greatest extent determine the safety of public places discussed above. When implementing smart city projects and their individual systems, the density and socio-ethnic composition of the population are primary factors and conditions whose characteristics largely determine the influence of secondary factors – development and equipment with technical security equipment.

Technical equipment is the simplest and most affordable way to solve the problems of public places' security. With the proper organization of the response of law enforcement agencies to the signals of technical security systems, it seems possible in the shortest possible time to improve the safety indicators of public places, such as reducing the number of crimes in public places, identifying and neutralizing potential criminals, etc.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Thus, it is necessary to apply an integrated approach to ensuring safety in public places of the urban environment. Ensuring security depends on successful management at all levels of government, considering all influencing factors.

Today, the adoption of operational decisions regarding the development of urban public areas and, above all, the technical equipment of security equipment can have the greatest effect in organizing the security of public places. Effective control of such factors as population density and its socio-ethnic composition is hardly possible in the conditions of already existing urban areas without serious human rights violations. In matters of participation of all levels of government in ensuring the safety of public places, more powers in this area should be given to local self-government through the adoption of a law on municipal police and the organization of appropriate service.

Studies of world experience show that the active participation of local self-government in the protection of public safety on the ground contributes to the successful solution of problems. Thus, the research hypothesis has been proven. The problems of integrating activities to ensure the safety of public places within the framework of the Smart City system may be the prospect of future research.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+	+	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+	+	+	+	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+	+	+	+	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+	+	+	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+	+	+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+	+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	+	+	+	+	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation	+	+	+	+	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+	+	+	+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+	+	+	+	+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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